

Awareness, Usage and Influence of Social Media Platforms on Learning Effectiveness in Selected Public and Private Schools in Ogun State, Nigeria

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The advent of the digital age has ushered in a new era of technological advancement that has revolutionized various aspects of human life, including education. Social media platforms, with their immense popularity and diverse functionalities, have become integral to the daily lives of many, particularly the younger generation. These communication networks include social media platforms, such as Facebook, Instagram, and X formally known as Twitter, etc. The development of social media as a platform for communication can be traced back to the birth of the Internet, which encompasses the development of electronic mail (e-mail). While social media has primarily been associated with entertainment and social interaction, its potential for educational purposes has gained significant attention. Despite this potential, the educational benefits of social media remain a topic of debate among scholars, educators, and policymakers. In particular, the question of whether social media positively contributes to learning effectiveness or instead creates distractions and fosters superficial engagement remains unanswered. In Ogun State, Nigeria, there is a diversity in the types of schools available, with both public and private institutions offering varied resources and learning environments. This variety provides a unique opportunity to explore how students and educators in these different settings utilize social media for educational purposes and whether it influences learning effectiveness differently in public versus private institutions. This research investigated the level of awareness, usage and influence of social media platforms on learning effectiveness in selected public and private schools in Ogun State, Nigeria.

Keywords:
Social Media,
Awareness,
Usage,
Influence,
Secondary
School

Introduction

The educational system in Nigeria is faced by a myriad of challenges, part of which is the advent of social media platforms, which have sometimes led to a diversion in attention of both students and teachers, thus reducing the attention that is meant to be devoted to learning and academic activities. Social media forms an avenue through which individuals from different locations around the world can connect, interact, and share information. It requires

individuals to build an online profile to represent themselves to others in cyberspace. In recent years, the use of social media accounts such as Facebook, Snap chat, Instagram, etc. has increased drastically.

It is said that a third of the world's population is active on one form of social media or the other. Social media platforms are widely used by students, which can mainly be attributed to globalization and advancements in digital technology. Fuadyet *al.* (2021) posit that the

growth of social media in changing people's behaviour, perception, and attitudes, and the growth of online social technologies are driving audiences to become digitally friendly, changing user behaviour from passive to active, non-participatory to participatory, and enabling previously unknown or untapped users. Therefore, social media influences (s) almost everyone in the world, whether individuals, businesses, or society. Thus, providing equal opportunity to share thoughts, opinions, and information and enabling limitless networking opportunities, there is also the potential for frequent negative impacts of social media in Nigeria of today. For example and according to Chasanahet *al* (2022), students spend at least thirty minutes on Facebook per day. Prime *et al* (2020), asserted that the use of social media and its increase has created a new research platform, and it became clear that there is a need to further examine how social media can affect various aspects of learning. It is therefore pertinent to investigate how social media influences the learning effectiveness of secondary students, which invariably has a significant bearing on their academic achievement. Thus, the aim of this research is to ascertain the awareness, usage, and influence of social media platforms on learning effectiveness among public and private senior secondary school Students in the South-west and West Senatorial Districts of Ogun State, Nigeria.

Discussion

As the complexity of social media platforms are constantly changing, their definition broadens and continuously changes, making it difficult to assign a fixed definition to social media. For instance, Jacka & Scott (2011) argued that there is no single definition of social media. However, over the

years, many scholars have defined it from different perspectives. Kaplan & Haenlein (2012) defined social media as a group of Internet-based applications that build on the ideological and technological foundations of the World Wide Web (WWW) and allow the creation and exchange of user-generated content.

Social Media Definitions – common denominators

Sloan and Quan-Haase (2017) defined social media platforms as web-based services that allow individuals, communities, and organizations to collaborate, connect, interact, and build community by enabling them to create, co-create, modify, share, and engage with easily accessible user-generated content. According to Fuchs (2021), social media have rapidly changed the way people communicate with each other and have also become a means of connecting people in the social world as well as for educational purposes. Miller *et al.* (2016) defined social media as "the colonization of the space between traditional broadcast and private dyadic communication, providing people with a scale of group size and degrees of privacy that we have termed scalable sociality." Nations (2021); saw social media as a web-based communication tools that enable people to interact by sharing and consuming information. Although Nation's definition may be simplistic but it was able to capture the essence of social media platforms whose primary functions encompass the sharing and consuming of information and ideas. Matthew and Martinez (2014) defined social media as a set of online tools open for public membership that supports idea sharing, creating and editing content, and building relationships through interaction and collaboration. Similarly, Social media are web-based services that allow

individuals, communities, and organizations to collaborate, connect, interact, and build a community by enabling them to create, co-create, modify, share, and engage with easily accessible content (McCay-Peet and Quan-Haase, 2017). Mayfield (2017); posited that one can best understand social media as a group of new online media that enables wider participation (contributing information or contents and giving feedbacks), openness (almost no barrier accessing and making use of information), conversational (two-way communication), community (bonding and sharing common interests) and connectedness (linking other online tools or services/resources). Taprial and Kanwar (2012) made a comprehensive list and explained some of the characteristics of social media as follows:

Accessibility: social media is open and incurs negligible or no expenses. It was noted that they are easy to use and do not require extraordinary skills or knowledge to use; they are easy to associate with others. Therefore anyone with online access can participate in discussions.

1. **Interactivity:** Social media is of two-way or multi-communication that allows users to communicate with each other.
2. **Longevity:** Contents on social media are always available for a long period, if not forever.
3. **Reach:** Going by the word “reach,” Taprial and Kanwar meant that the internet offers unlimited reach to all available content that is, contents can be obtained anywhere it can be reached anywhere. Social media offers similar services to all users who can share anything with anyone they like.
4. **Speed:** Content created on social media is available to everyone as soon as it is published. For example, when an article is published, it is available anyone,

anywhere to download. One can also communicate quickly without external hindrance to the message delivery. The responses are instantaneous and simultaneous.

5. **Volatility:** Contents on social media can be edited or changed at anytime. Therefore, if one likes a specific product and acknowledges it on the platform, the user can always change his/her opinion anytime, which may apply to posts on Facebook where the user can delete or edit its contents anytime and anywhere.

Social Media Awareness and Usage

Some social media tools include: Yahoo Mail, Facebook, YouTube, WhatsApp, Instagram, Google, Zoom, and Twitter. Recent investigations on the use of social media have shown that approximately three billion individuals worldwide are now communicating via social media (Iwamoto and Chun, 2020). This growing population of social media users is spending an increasing amount of time on social network groupings, as facts and figures show that individuals spend two hours a day, on average, on a variety of social media applications, exchanging pictures and messages, updating status, tweeting, favouring, and commenting on updated socially shared information (Abbott, 2017).

In the same vein, Kaplan and Haenlein (2010) classified social media into six different classes as follows: *Blogs and micro blogs; Collaborative projects; Content communities; social gaming world; Social Networking sites; and Virtual Social World.*

Blogs/Micro Blogs

A blog is a web-based distribution of occasional articles, usually in reverse chronological order (OECD, 2007). It is a

type of website that is commonly maintained by a person with regular commentary entries, descriptions of events, or other materials such as graphics or videos.

A blog can be a journal, diary, 'what's new' page, or connections to different sites. It is normally open to people, and many people are free to create it. This is the work of one person; however, group blogs are also available. They are personal web pages and can vary from personal diaries to summaries of relevant information on a particular content area (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). Blogs also offer opportunities to interact with readers. Readers can post comments like in a visitor's book. Blogs can also be regarded as a form of personal publishing on the Internet. Often, subject or diary forms typically combine text and graphics, with links to other materials and easy web publishing. Blogs provide an appearance of anonymity while allowing human connections via commenting. These records are permanent. It can contain personal information (names, birthdays, towns, team names, phone numbers, and dorms). However, blogs can create avenues for harassment and bullying (through blog posts) and libel suits, whereas others can reuse a person's information for criminal or illegal acts (Valie, 2006). Blogs, however, might be a better instrument to achieve idea sharing and collaborative learning, without sacrificing too much on customizing blogging space, tuning its look and feel, and the sense of ownership (Hall and Davison 2007).

Examples of blogs include:- My Opera, Plurk, Twitter, Vox, Wooxie, Personal blogs (e.g., lindaikeji blog). Micro blogging sites are social media platforms that allow users to write brief texts, update and publish them. Twitter is an example of a micro blogging site.

Twitter was founded on the 21st of March 2006 by Jack Dorsey and Noah Glass. Twitter is an online social networking site that allows users to send and read text-based posts. From this conception, these texts were limited to 140 text characters but on November 7, 2017, the limit was doubled to 280 characters. These texts are known as "tweets". Users also follow the updates of friends they "follow" - send them direct messages, and reply publicly to friends, or just post questions or comments as their current status (Sorav, J. (2010).

Collaborative Projects: Collaborative projects enable the joint and simultaneous creation of content by many end-users (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). Fama (1970) (as cited in Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010) believed that the main idea underlying collaborative projects is that the joint effort of numerous actors prompts a better outcome than individual actors.

Kaplan and Haenlein (2014) identified four types of collaborative projects. The first type is wikis. Examples of wikis include: Familypedia, WikiHow, Wikipedia, Wikiquote, Wikitravel. The second category is social bookmarking sites, or collaborative tagging services. Examples of social bookmarking sites include: CiteULike, Deliciou, Digg, Google Bookmarks, and Pinboard. The third category is online forums and message boards. Examples of online forums are the: confidential college, student's edge, student room, and Yahoo groups. The fourth site was the review sites. Examples of review sites include:- Epinions, Glassdoor, Judy's Book, RateMyProfessors, RateMyTeachers.com, and Trip Advisors.

Social Gaming World: Social gaming world is a platform that replicates a three-dimensional environment that can appear in

the form of personalized avatars and interact with each other as they would in real life (Kaplan, A & Haenlein, M, 2010). An example of a social game world media platform is World Warcraft.

Wikipedia defines social gaming as “playing online games that allow or require social interaction between players”. The Collins dictionary defines social gaming as “the activity of playing online games with other members of the same online group”. The Oxford dictionary defines Social Gaming as “the activity or practice of playing an online game on a social media platform, with a major emphasis on friends and community involvement”. Social Gaming ranges from tending a farm to playing soldiers in combat. Ideas for new games are constantly under development. Some popular social games include adventure, arcade style games, casino style games, and role- playing. *Social Network Sites*: Social networks are Internet- or mobile-based social spaces where people can connect, communicate, and create and share content with others. Social networks are strong tools for social interaction and connection, where they can improve family ties and friends in a rich social context. Social networks are the main application under the umbrella of social media, which comes with the era of Web 2.0.

Positive Influence and Negative Influence

Several studies have affirmed that social media plays a vital role for students in higher education, including the research conducted by Wheeler, Yeomans, and Wheeler (2008); Rifkin, Longnecker, Leach, and Ortia (2009). Their study recognized four (4) significant advantages of social media usage by students in higher education: enhancing relationships, improving learning motivation, offering personalized course material, and developing collaborative abilities. Social media has

contributed significantly to facilitating learning in the 21st century. A more significant percentage of students, including those at the Ph.D. level, commonly use social media to improve their studies (Khan, 2010). Jain, Verma, Verma, and Tiwari (2012), in their research titled "The Impact of social networking in promoting education," revealed that students benefit from chatting with other students, teachers, and external sources to acquire knowledge. Yunus and Salehi (2012) argued in the same direction that students gained more vocabulary, improved their writing skills, and reduced their spelling mistakes through social media usage.

As an educational tool, social media enriches learning by allowing students and teachers to connect in new and fascinating ways, encouraging a flexible learning mode. Flexible learning expands the choice of what, when, and how people learn. It supports different learning styles, including e-learning, which is highly patronized worldwide (Pappas, 2013). In their study, other scholars, O'Keeffe and Clake-Pearson (2011), also revealed that social media benefits students by connecting them to one another on assignments and class projects.

It is further bolstered in Arquero and Esteban (2013) and Selwyn (2007), who concluded that social media undoubtedly generate new opportunities to engage students in higher education as they are remarkably effective at connecting people and facilitating the exchange of information.

According to research carried out by Jain; Verma, Verma, and Tiwari (2012), it revealed that some students benefit from chit-chatting with other students, instructors, and social relations as a means of connecting with others. This is also supported by Yunus and Salehi (2012), who both argued in the same

trend that students learn and improve on their vocabulary, reading, and writing skills and the correction of their spelling errors through social media usage. In addition, it deepens learning by creating a wider range of options to explore by both the students and instructors, which is done at their own convenience on the choice on what methodology is best suited in the teaching-learning process. Some of the options include:- online teaching-learning, which is becoming more popular and accessible anywhere in the world through internet connection. O'keeffe and Clake-Pearson (2011), discovered that students can also share, solve, and discuss class activities, assignments, and group projects on social media within or outside the school premises. It is further propped by Arquero and Esteban (2013) and Selwyn (2007), who posited that social media has unquestionably created innovative prospects to engage students in secondary education as they are remarkably effective at connecting people, thereby expediting the exchange of information. According to Gudelliwar (2019), social media platforms enable teachers and students to collaborate, interact, or communicate with others and access online resources. It improves students' grades and reduces class absenteeism, affecting academic grades and performance. Lecturers and students can learn through social media, which assists them in sharing content and connectivity (Alhababi *et al.*, 2015). Kolhar *et al.* (2021) and Alnjadat, Hmaidi, Samha, Kilani, and Hasswan (2021) suggested that students are recorded as one of the largest users on social media platforms daily for everyday tasks (activities). Gudelliwar, *et al.* (2017) found that 51% of students used social media for academic assignments, whereas 60% used it for academic topic discussions. According to

Alnjadat, Hmaidi, Samha, Kilani, and Hasswan (2021), social media usage increases students' academic performance. Apart from the increase in usage, users' (students') culture affects the adoption of SMPs in higher education institutions (Balakrishnan 2017).

However, it was observed in Kuppuswamy and Shankar's study of 2010, it was observed that the uncultured use of these social media platforms also affects students' use of English and grammar, which makes students abbreviate verbal and non-verbal words in their chat rooms and also in the class rooms Obi, Bulus, Adamu, & Sala'at, (2012). Most students' use social media slangs, while some are accustomed to using them in day-to-day communication with their peers due to the rampant usage of unnecessary abbreviation of spellings, which could have a detrimental impact on their morals and academic achievement. Further observation shows that some students get too carried away with the usage as they go as far as using such words and it's abbreviation in the classroom activities by constructing sentences like „Be right back as BRB“, „Rolling on the floor laughing as ROFL“, Shaking my head as SMH“, “As soon as possible as ASAP” and so on. There are students“ who use those aforementioned words in their examinations which makes their teachers mark them down. The popularity of social media and the speed at which information is published have created a lax attitude towards proper spelling and grammar. This reduces a student's ability to effectively write without relying on a computer's spell-checking feature. For example, it is common to see youngsters chatting in sensitive and highly organized places such as religious places, streets, public vehicles and lecture rooms. Some are carried away and chat while walking along

highways. In addition, the major challenge is that students now find it difficult to write long essays and even when they write, most words are abbreviated.

Studies indicate that students' exposure to the Internet may breed intellectual laziness as they tend to become over-reliant on it. Some students depend on finding ready-made answers to class assignments instead of engaging in intellectual rigour. This can lead to intellectual laziness and make them unproductive when ICTs are unavailable (Omenugha, 2010). Many students rely on the accessibility of information on social media and the Web to provide answers. This implies a reduced focus on learning and retaining information. Our ability to retain information has decreased, and our willingness to spend more time researching and looking up good information has decreased because we have become accustomed to the ease of accessibility to information on social media.

In addition, students who attempt multiple-tasks, checking social media sites while studying, show reduced academic performance. Their ability to concentrate on the task at hand is significantly reduced by the distractions brought about by YouTube, Facebook, or Twitter. Odii (2013) argued that social media use could easily become so engaging that users would spend hours at a spot, on a stretch, without realizing it. This addiction to social media, especially among students, portends danger as it reduces the amount of time devoted to studies.

Taking this notion of distractive addiction from another perspective, Omenugha (2010) reported that some students exposed to learning by digital avenues developed addiction and were unable to cope with conventional learning realities. The more time students spend on social sites, the less

time they spend socializing in person;- Because of the lack of body signals and other nonverbal cues such as, tone and inflection, social networking sites are not an adequate replacement for face-to-face communication. Therefore, students who spend a great deal of time on social networking are less able to communicate effectively.

Previous Meta-analyses

Several previous studies have been conducted on social media and the social behaviour of youths. For example, the research on "Uses and influence of social media on undergraduate students in Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile Ife, Nigeria in 2019, by Subair *et al.*, revealed that Internet addiction and distraction are the major influences of social media on undergraduate studies. Similarly, the findings indicated that undergraduates used social media platforms mainly for socialization, information, and academic purposes. The reason is not far from the priority that the undergraduate students of Obafemi Awolowo University placed on the purposes of using social media platforms. This perhaps explains the extent of the influence that social media platforms have on their studies. The studies of Subair, Solomon and Oreoluwa (2019) and Zahid, Ahmad, Syed and Faisal (2016) on impact of social media on student's academic performance revealed that, social media enable flexible course of learning as it gives opportunity to students including those at the postgraduate level to share ideas, opinions and interact with friends as well as express their worries and concerns over their studies.

Subair *et al* found that undergraduate students spent an average of two to three hours daily on social media platforms. This may explain the extent of internet addiction among undergraduates. Similarly, Hashem and El-Badawy (2015) indicated that 50% of students spent one to three hours studying a day, and 33%

spent the same amount of time on social media per day. The findings revealed that the surveyed undergraduate students used social media platforms for socialization more than for academic purposes and is in agreement of the findings from Ugyen and Tshering (2021) discovered in their study that those who spent more time on social media spent less time studying. In the same vein, Hashim and Kutbi (2015) found that social media, when well integrated into human society, has both positive and negative aspects; some of which include promoting fraud, cybercrime, cyber bullying, and weakening physical human relationships. Likewise, Rajeev & Jobilal (2015) stated that youth do not usually use the good side of social media; they are tilted towards the downside. Moreover, the result of the research of Lowisz, (2014) also stated that instead of using social media for positive communication and the benefits of connectivity, youths use it to the contrary. The research concluded that students who are at their growing stage need to be well monitored and guided by parents and guardians, but they are left in the hands of technological development.

Method

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design; that involved gathering data, describing events and organizing, tabulating, depicting and describing the data collected. The descriptive survey was adopted because the respondents were located from different public and private secondary schools in Ogun State, Nigeria who could not be directly observed. Therefore, the survey was cross-sectional and a questionnaire instrument was adopted to carry out the survey.

The research instruments used for this study included three different questionnaires for each variable, these questionnaires included

the Social media awareness and learning effectiveness Questionnaire (SMALEQ), the Usage of social media and Learning Effectiveness Questionnaire (USMLEQ) and the Influence of Social on Learning effectiveness Questionnaire (ISMLEQ). Each of the questionnaire was divided into two sections consisting of **Section A and B**. **Section A** was designed to collect data about respondents' background information while **Section B** of each questionnaire was design to collect information of the awareness, usage and influence of social media platforms on the learning effectiveness selected public and private schools in Ogun West and Abeokuta South Senatorial Zone, Nigeria. The modified Likert-type opinion scale whose response options will include: strongly agree, agree, disagree and strongly disagree was adopted. The content validity method was utilized so as to ascertain the extent to which the items in the research instrument represent the content and behavior specified by the theoretical concept being measured. The instrument was validated through the process of a pre-test, during which time it was administered on students of secondary schools in a local government different from the target locations where the study was finally conducted. The questionnaire was therefore validated through the inputs received from the above layers of intervention. The test re-test method was adopted to determine the consistency and reliability of the research instruments. A Test re-test study was carried out by administering Questionnaire in three selected secondary schools in Ado-Odo Ota Local Government, Ogun State, The selected schools for the Test re-test were not included in the respondents when the final study was carried out.

Findings

Descriptive Statistics for answering Research Question

Table1: Frequency Distribution of Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Demographic Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Age	12-14	98	24.5%
	15-17	282	70.5%
	18-20	20	5.0%
Gender	Male	213	53.25%
	Female	187	46.75%
Class	S.S.S One	126	31.5%
	S.S.S Two	186	46.5%
	S.S.S Three	88	22%
Schools	Ilogbo Community High School	100	25%
	Asero High School	100	25%
	Ambassador College	100	25%
	Taidob College	100	25%
Type of School	Public Secondary School	200	50%
	Private Secondary School	200	50%

Source: Fieldwork (2024)

Table 1 shows the demographic distribution of the research respondents indicating that 98 (24.5%) of the respondents were between the age of 12-14, 282(70.5%) were between the ages of 15-17, while 18-20 years of age made for the remaining 5.0% of the sample population. The demographic distribution as indicated in Table 1 also, showed that the research participants consisted of 213 (53.25%) male students and 187 (46.25%)female students thus indicating

that the sample population comprised more male than female students.

In addition, the distribution shown in table 1, reveals that each secondary school to be reviewed included two private and two public secondary schools consisting of hundred (100) students each. Therefore, each school which consists of Ilogbo Community High School, Asero High School, Taidob College and Ambassador College made up 25% of the sample population.

Research Question One

What is the level of awareness of social media platforms among students in selected

public and private schools in Ogun State, Nigeria?

Table 1: Social Media Awareness among students of Public and Private secondary schools

S/N	Social Media Awareness	Fully Aware	Aware	Not Aware	Fully not Aware	Mean	Standard Deviation	Decision
1.	Facebook	313 (78.25%)	87 (21.25%)	–	–	7.8	.41	Fully Aware
2.	Whats App	380 (95.0%)	17 (4.25%)	3 (0.75%)	–	7.9	.26	Fully Aware
3.	Youtube	208 (52.0%)	106 (26.5%)	69 (17.25)	17 (4.25%)	7.3	0.89	Fully Aware
4.	LinkedIn	78 (19.5%)	114 (28.5%)	115 (28.75%)	93 (23.25%)	6.4	1.05	Aware
5.	Tiktok	397 (99.25%)	3 (0.75%)	–	–	7.9	0.086	Fully Aware
6	Instagram	140 (35%)	260 (65%)	–	–	7.3	0.47	Fully Aware
7.	Twitter	131 (32.75%)	168 (42.0%)	58 (14.5%)	43 (10.75%)	6.9	0.95	Aware
8.	Reddit	85 (21.25%)	73 (18.25%)	170 (42.5%)	72 (18.0%)	6.4	1.01	Aware
9.	Discord	23 (5.75%)	15 (3.75%)	114 (28.5%)	248 (62.0%)	5.5	0.81	Not aware
10.	Goodreads	1 (0.25%)	8 (2.0%)	222 (55.5%)	169 (42.25%)	5.6	0.54	Not aware
11.	Pinterest	41 (10.255)	37 (9.25%)	81 (20.25%)	241 (60.25%)	5.6	1.0	Not aware
12.	Letterbox	72 (18.0%)	73 (18.25%)	110 (27.5%)	145 (36.25%)	6.1	1.11	Aware
13.	Meetup	65 (16.25%)	93 (22.25%)	168 (42.0%)	74 (18.5%)	6.3	0.93	Aware
14.	Snapchat	320 (80.0%)	39 (9.75%)	41 (10.25%)	-	7.6	0.64	Fully Aware
15.	Telegram	225 (56.25%)	91 (22.75%)	50 (12.5%)	35 (8.5%)	7.2	0.98	Fully Aware
16.	Quora	94 (23.5%)	51 (12.75%)	160 (40.0%)	95 (23.75%)	6.4	1.08	Aware

17.	Bereal	3 (0.75%)	33 (8.25%)	122 (30.5%)	242 (60.5%)	5.5	0.68	Not aware
18.	Messenger	107 (26.75%)	127 (31.75%)	131 (32.75%)	35 (8.75%)	6.7	0.94	Aware
19.	Twitch	30 (7.5%)	76 (19.0%)	175 (43.75%)	119 (29.75%)	6.04	0.88	Aware
20.	Tumblr	19 (4.75%)	86 (21.5%)	103 (25.75%)	192 (48.0%)	5.8	0.93	Not aware
21.	Flickr	69 (17.25%)	101 (25.25%)	67 (16.75%)	163 (40.75%)	6.1	1.14	Not aware
22.	Wechat	101 (25.25%)	103 (25.75%)	150 (37.5%)	46 (11.5%)	6.6	0.98	Aware
23.	Weibo	23 (5.8%)	68 (17.0%)	196 (49.0%)	113 (28.2%)	6.0	0.83	Not aware
24.	Sharechat	45 (11.3%)	59 (14.75%)	143 (35.5%)	154 (38.5%)	5.9	0.99	Not aware
25.	Clubhouse	42 (10.5%)	62 (15.5%)	122 (30.5%)	174 (43.5%)	5.9	1.0	Not aware

Key; Fully Aware (F.A) =8, Aware (A) =7, Not Aware (N.A) = 6, fully not Aware (F.N.A) = 5

Weighted Mean= 156.94/25=6.3

Source: Fieldwork (2024)

Table 1 shows data on the level of social media awareness among public and private senior secondary school students in Ogun State. A modified Likert rating scale of Fully Aware (8), Aware (7), Not Aware (6) and fully not Aware (5) was adopted, where the weighted mean of 6.3 was used as the criterion mean. Twenty-five items were used to determine the level of social media awareness of public and private senior secondary school students in Ogun state, Nigeria. The findings from table 1, revealed that majority of the respondents are “fully aware” Facebook as a social media platform with a mean of 7.8. Table 1 also indicates that senior secondary school students in Ogun state, Nigeria are “fully aware” of social media platforms such as Whats App, YouTube, Tiktok, Instagram, LinkedIn, Reddit, messenger, Snapchat, Telegram and

Twitter with mean of 7.9,7.3, 7.9, 7.3, 6.4, 6.3, 6.7, 7.6, 7.2 and 6.9 respectively. However, table 1 further reveals that the majority of senior secondary school students in Ogun State, Nigeria are not aware of social media platforms such as Discord, Goodreads, Pinterest, Letterbox, Meetup, Bereal, Twitch, Tumblr, Flickr, Weibo, Sharechat and clubhouse whose means are below the mean of 6.3.

Drawing on the results as indicated in table 1, majority of the research respondents are “aware” of sixteen(16) social media platform out of the twenty (25) social media platform outlined in the research instrument. This implies that senior secondary school students in Ogun State, Nigeria are aware of 64% of the social media platform outlined in the research instrument as shown in table 1. Thus, answering research question one which

states that “What is the level of awareness of social media platforms among students in selected public and private schools in Ogun State, Nigeria?”

Research Question Two:

What social media platforms commonly used among students in selected public and private schools in Ogun State, Nigeria?

Research Question Three: What activities are carried out on social media platforms among students in selected public and private schools in Ogun State, Nigeria?

Table 2: Social Media Usage among senior secondary school students in Ogun State, Nigeria

S/N	Social Media Platform Usage	Academics	Seek Informa tion	Social/ Entertai nment	Mean	Standard Deviation	Decision
1.	Facebook	143 (35.75%)	118 (29.5%)	139 (34.75%)	10.8	0.84	Academic
2.	Whats App	81 (20.25%)	116 (20.9%)	203 (50.7%)	10.3	0.79	Entertainment
3.	Youtube	136 (34.0%)	123 (30.75%)	141 (35.25%)	10.0	0.83	Entertainment
4.	LinkedIn	91 (22.75%)	168 (42.0%)	141 (35.25%)	10.1	0.75	Entertainment
5.	Tiktok	10 (2.5%)	76 (19.0%)	314 (78.5%)	10.7	0.48	Entertainment
6.	Instagram	16 (4.0%)	75 (18.75%)	309 (77.25%)	10.7	0.53	Entertainment
7.	Twitter	7 (1.8%)	192 (48.0%)	201 (50.2%)	10.5	0.53	Entertainment
8.	Reddit	40 (10.0%)	206 (51.5%)	154 (38.5%)	10.3	0.64	Seek Information
9.	Discord	1 (0.25%)	1 (0.25%)	398 (99.5%)	10.9	0.11	Entertainment
10.	Goodreads	97 (24.25%)	136 (34.0%)	167 (41.75%)	10.2	0.79	Entertainment
11.	Pinterest	201 (50.2%)	195 (48.8%)	4 (1.0%)	9.5	0.52	Academics
12.	Letterbox	67 (16.75%)	123 (30.75%)	210 (52.5%)	10.4	0.75	Entertainment
13.	Meetup	173 (43.25%)	59 (14.75%)	168 (42.0%)	9.9	0.93	Academics
14.	Snapchat	33 (8.25%)	44 (11.0%)	323 (80.75%)	10.7	0.60	Entertainment
15.	Telegram	76	115	209	10.3	0.78	Entertainment

		(19.0%)	(28.7%)	(52.3%)			
16.	Quora	118 (29.5%)	191 (47.8%)	91 (22.8%)	9.9	0.72	Seek Information
17.	Bereal	181 (45.25%)	103 (25.75%)	119 (29.0%)	9.8	0.85	Academics
18.	Messenger	76 (19.0%)	168 (42.0%)	156 (39.0%)	10.2	0.74	Seek information
19.	Twitch	152 (38.0%)	83 (20.75%)	165 (41.25%)	10.0	0.89	Entertainment
20.	Tumblr	108 (27.0%)	122 (30.5%)	170 (42.5%)	10.2	0.82	Entertainment
21.	Flickr	119 (29.75%)	171 (42.75%)	110 (27.5%)	9.9	0.76	Seek information
22.	Wechat	52 (13.0%)	168 (42.0%)	180 (45.0%)	10.3	0.69	Entertainment
23.	Weibo	147 (36.75%)	183 (45.75)	70 (17.5%)	9.8	0.71	Seek Information
24.	Sharechat	158 (39.5%)	74 (18.5%)	168 (42.0%)	10.0	0.90	Entertainment
25.	Clubhouse	85 (21.25%)	165 (41.25%)	150 (37.5%)	10.1	0.75	Seek information

KEY; Academics (A) = 11, Seek Information (S.I) = 10, Social/entertainment = 9

Weighted Mean= 254.6/25= 10.1

Source: Fieldwork (2024)

Table 2 shows data on the usage of social media platforms among senior secondary school students in Ogun State. A modified Likert rating scale of Academic (11), Seek information (10), and Social/entertainment (9) was adopted to identify what senior secondary school students use social media platforms, with a weighted mean of 10.1. The findings from table 2, reveal that the majority of respondents make use of most social media platforms for “social/entertain”. Out of twenty-five (25) social media platform outlined above, fifteen (15) of them are used for “social/entertainment”, some of these social media platform include WhatsApp, YouTube, Tiktok and Instagram. On the other hand, only six (6) out of twenty-five

(25) social media platforms are used by senior secondary school students in Ogun state, Nigeria to “seek information” these platforms included Reddit, messenger, Quora etc. while the remaining four (4) platform are adopted for academic. Thus, we provided answers to research question two.

In furtherance to the above, Table 2 also provides answer to research question three which states “What are the activities carried out on social media platforms among students in selected public and private schools in Ogun State, Nigeria?” by revealing that most social media platforms are commonly used for social/ entertainment by senior secondary school students in Ogun State, Nigeria.

Research Question Four:

What are the influences of gender on the level of social media among awareness students in

selected public and private schools in Ogun State, Nigeria?

Table 3: Gender awareness of social media Platforms

	Gender	N	Percentage (%)	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Social Media Awareness	Male	213	53.3	6.5294	.36369	.02492
	Female	187	46.8	7.5745	.31829	.02328

Table 3 shows the difference in the influence of gender on the level of awareness of social media among students of selected public and private senior secondary schools in Ogun State, Nigeria.

Table 3 shows the mean score of 6.5294 for social media awareness of male senior secondary school students in selected schools in Ogun State, Nigeria and that of female students was 7.5745. This implies that there is a statistically significant difference in the influences of gender on the level of awareness of social media among students in

selected public and private schools in Ogun State, Nigeria.

Thus indicates that female senior secondary school students in some selected schools in Ogun State, Nigeria are more aware of social media platforms than male senior secondary school students, with a mean difference of -1.0451.

Research Question Five

How does the influence of social of social media on learning effectiveness compare between students in the selected public and private school in Ogun state, Nigeria?

Table 4: Difference in the influence of Social Media on Learning Effectiveness between public and Private schools

	Type of School	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Learning Effectiveness	Public senior secondary School	200	18.7700	.21135	.01494
	Private senior secondary School	200	18.7774	.17348	.01227

Source: Fieldwork (2024)

Table 4 showed the differences in the influence of social media on learning effectiveness compare between students in the selected public and private school in Ogun state, Nigeria.

Table 4 showed the mean score of 18.7700 for learning effectiveness for senior

secondary school students in the selected public schools in Ogun state, Nigeria and that of private senior secondary school students is 18.7774. This implied that there is no significant statistical difference in the influence of social media on learning effectiveness between senior secondary

students in public schools and senior secondary school students in private schools in Ogun state, Nigeria.

The above result, therefore provided an answer to research question five which states “How does the influence of social of social media on learning effectiveness compare between students in the selected public and private school in Ogun state, Nigeria?” as indicated by a mean difference 0.0074. Thus revealing that senior secondary school students in private schools are marginally more influenced by social media with respect to their learning effectiveness as compared to senior secondary school students in public schools in Ogun state Nigeria, however this difference is no significant.

Summary of Results

The result of the tested hypothesis above reveals that Levene’s test consisting of an f-value of 10.888 and sig value of .0521, which is higher than the significance level of .05 showing that the variance of in public and private secondary schools students are close in equality. This implies that the distribution of competency score of public secondary school students is similar in shape to the distribution of competency score for private secondary school students in Ogun State, Nigeria. In addition, this revealed a significant value of $.0621 > .05$ and a mean difference of $-.00740$. Based on the results as shown in the table above, the research hypothesis five (H_{05}) which state that “The influence of social media on learning effectiveness does not significantly differ between public and private school students in Ogun State, Nigeria” is therefore accepted (p. value $> .05$). This implies that there is no statistically significant difference in the influence of social media on learning effectiveness between public secondary

school student and private schools students in Ogun State, Nigeria.

Discussion and Conclusion

Students who attempt to multiple-tasks, checking social media sites while studying, show reduced academic performance. Their ability to concentrate on the task at hand is significantly reduced by the distractions brought about by YouTube, Facebook or Twitter e.t.c. Ugyen and Tshering (2021) discovered in their study that those who spent more time on social media spent less time studying. In the same vein, Hashim and Kutbi (2015) found that social media, when well integrated into human society, has both positive and negative aspects; some of which include promoting fraud, cybercrime, cyber bullying, and weakening physical human relationships. Likewise, Rajeev & Jobilal (2015) stated that youth do not usually use the good side of social media; they are tilted towards the downside. Moreover, the result of the research of Lowisz, (2014) also stated that instead of using social media for positive communication and the benefits of connectivity, youths use it to the contrary. Omenugha (2010) reported that some students exposed to learning by digital avenues developed addiction and were unable to cope with conventional learning realities. The more time students spend on social sites, the less time they spend socializing in person;- Because of the lack of body signals and other nonverbal cues such as, tone and inflection, social networking sites are not an adequate replacement for face-to-face communication. Therefore, students who spend a great deal of time on social networking are less able to communicate effectively. It was also discussed, that students needs proper monitoring to use social media platforms, especially students who are at their growing

stage need to be well monitored and guided by parents and guardians, but they are left in the hands of technological development

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